

PRO-CLIMATE

Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change

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D4.2 KPIs to Measure Changes in Capacity with Respect to Climate Resilience

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D4.2 KPIs to measure changes in capacity with respect to climate resilience

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D4.2 KPIs to measure changes in capacity with respect to climate resilience

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Abbreviations

CA	Change Agent
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPIs	Key Performance Indicator(s)
REA	European Research Executive Agency
SMART	Specific Measurable Achievable Relevant Time-bound
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SES	Social-Ecological Systems
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document is produced as part of the PRO-CLIMATE project, Deliverable 4.2 (D4.2) describes the robust framework for designing effective methodologies and tools to proactively foster adaptive behaviours and facilitate transformative changes used in this project. Good governance measures are aligned with the intended behavioural changes in each Living Lab (LL). The specific focus for this document is the KPIs used to measure changes in capacity with respect to climate resilience through different forms of behavioural change. The importance of KPIs is emphasised and the SMART framework is used for developing effective KPIs that are specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time-bounded. Synergy between behavioural change and good governance is essential for promoting climate resilience. By embedding behavioural change initiatives within governance mechanisms iteratively, the project ensures that interventions are not only effective but also enduring.

The approach used to design and implement the KPIs is one or multi-scale integration alignment of local, regional, and European-level frameworks to ensure that the KPIs developed in the project are universally relevant while being adaptable to the specific socio-ecological challenges of individual LLs. The process is co-creative with cross-disciplinary collaboration. Progress is tracked and effectiveness is assessed with the adaptation of strategies over time.

The KPIs framework is designed to help Living Lab (LL) leaders and Change Agents effectively measure governance impact, adaptability, sustainability, behavioural change, and capacity-building efforts over time which requires a structured approach for selecting KPIs that reflect the LL specific context. The four themes (Governance Structure, Governance Processes, Governance Culture and Governance Outcomes) that the framework is structured around align with the SES framework. Each LL will determine their own KPIs that align to the context of their case study. The collaborative approach to determining the KPIs is fostered through close working with WP2 and WP3 and with the LL leaders. In addition, WP4 provides support for LLs through workshops, suites of correspondence and regular progress meetings.

Ultimately, this integrated approach will empower communities to build climate-resilient futures and contribute to the broader goal of sustainable development.

1 Introduction

1.1 The PRO-CLIMATE Project

The PRO-CLIMATE (Proactive Community Adaptation to Climate Change through Social Transformation and Behavioural Change) project aims to support communities in proactively adapting to climate change through social transformation and behavioural change. To achieve this, PRO-CLIMATE will identify social tipping points and policy actions to enable systemic transformation to be achieved across social systems. PRO-CLIMATE adopts an approach guided by the concept of systems thinking, which views communities as complex systems influenced by multiple socio-economic and environmental factors. By understanding and leveraging the communities' dynamics, PRO-CLIMATE's approach develops strategies and interventions that promote social transformation and behavioural change. This results in a robust framework for designing effective methodologies and tools to proactively foster adaptive behaviours and facilitate transformative changes.

A set of diverse case studies across Europe will be used to co-create, validate, and upscale this framework by running LLs and bringing stakeholders together to understand community governance and institutional structures. These case studies will also pilot and validate the project's behavioural change activities. The outputs of PRO-CLIMATE include:

- a) Identification of key components of climate adaptation systems, their interactions, systemic interdependencies, and trade-offs.
- b) Design, implementation, and evaluation of a Living Lab framework.
- c) Identification of social tipping points and leverage actions for policymakers.
- d) Development of a multi-agent computer model for European socio-ecological systems to allow realistic analysis of existing and future policy scenarios likely to produce systemic transformations.
- e) Policy recommendations to accelerate systemic change.

1.2 Description of WP4

In the PRO-CLIMATE project, Work Package 4 (WP4: Good governance and behavioural change) aims to foster significant and sustainable change within the Living Lab communities. Its objectives are to:

- **Empower Behavioural Change:** Enabling stakeholders in Living Lab communities to initiate and sustain climate-resilient behaviours through tailored toolkits and events.
- **Develop Learning Communities:** Creating learning assets to transform communities into resilient, knowledge-sharing organisations that lead climate adaptation efforts.
- **Enhance Change Capacity:** Strengthening individual, organisational, and institutional capacities for effective climate change responses.
- **Share Good Practices:** Developing and disseminating a replicable process to support sustainable change, ensuring that best practices are shared widely across the PRO-CLIMATE project.

1.3 Scope of the Document

This document focuses on developing various KPIs to allow the measurement of changes in capacity with respect to climate resilience through behavioural change. Following familiarisation with the LLs and their intended behavioural changes, this task aligns good governance measures with the agreed intended behavioural changes in each Living Lab. This integration stage allows for a review of the measures and extent of change capacity through audit assessments, to ensure the systematic transformation to climate resilience.

2 Importance of KPIs for Measuring Behavioural Change and Good Governance

2.1 What Are KPIs and Why Are They Important?

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are quantifiable metrics used to evaluate the extent of the successes of an organisation, project, or initiative in achieving its strategic objectives (e.g. Parmenter, 2015). In the context of climate resilience, these KPIs provide a standardised framework for assessing progress towards enhancing adaptive capacity, promoting behavioural change, and ensuring effective governance (Mosca et al, 2023; Engle et al., 2014).

By establishing clear KPIs, stakeholders can identify areas requiring improvement, monitor ongoing efforts, and ensure accountability. KPIs are essential for:

- **Performance Measurement:** Tracking progress toward climate resilience goals by measuring tangible and intangible outcomes.
- **Comparative Analysis:** Facilitating comparison between different communities, projects, or time periods to evaluate effectiveness and understanding of differences pertaining to communities, projects and time periods.
- **Decision-Making:** Providing reliable and meaningful data to inform evidence-based policy-making and eventually planning and development of effective strategies.
- **Accountability and Transparency:** Demonstrating the effectiveness of interventions to all stakeholders and the general public.
- **Continuous Improvement:** Enabling iterative refinement of strategies based on real-world feedback from relevant stakeholders and measurable outcomes.

In PRO-CLIMATE the KPI framework developed within WP4, focuses at the Living Lab Level (LL Level) in the context of co-designing these KPIs.

2.2 The SMART Approach to KPIs

The SMART framework is a widely recognised tool for developing effective KPIs (e.g. Ishak et al, 2019; Angelakoglou et al., 2019). This framework ensures that each developed KPI meets the following criteria:

- **Specific:** Clearly defined and unambiguous, detailing precisely what is being measured and why it is relevant. For example, rather than stating “Increase Awareness”, a specific KPI would be “Increase the number of participants that attend an “awareness campaign” by for example fishers in case study X by 10%”.
- **Measurable:** Quantifiable, allowing progress to be tracked over time. It requires defining appropriate metrics and data collection methods. For instance, measuring the “Number of stakeholders trained” or the “Percentage of local policies adapted for climate resilience.”
- **Achievable:** Realistic and attainable, considering available resources, capacity, and timeframes. Setting overly ambitious KPIs can be counterproductive, leading to discouragement and resource wastage.
- **Relevant:** Aligned with the overall objectives of the project. KPIs must contribute meaningfully to climate resilience and behavioural change goals rather than serving as superficial metrics.
- **Time-bound:** Having a clear timeline for achievement. Deadlines help maintain momentum and provide reference points for evaluating progress. For instance, “Achieve a 30% increase in community awareness within 12 months”.

Applying the SMART approach ensures that KPIs are not only well-designed but also actionable and aligned with the broader goals of the PRO-CLIMATE project. It provides a structured methodology for defining success, evaluating progress, and making necessary adjustments.

2.3 Aligning Good Governance Measures with Behavioural Change

A cornerstone of the project's approach is the emphasis on good governance within our established Living Lab communities. Good governance refers to the establishment of formal and informal rules, institutions, and processes that facilitate transparent, inclusive, and effective decision-making (e.g. Aguilera & Cuervo-Cazurra, 2004; Aguilera & Cuervo-Cazurra, 2009). These elements are essential for advancing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and fostering a governance structure that supports sustainable development.

Good governance plays a crucial role in fostering behavioural change by creating the enabling environment that enables communities to engage in climate-resilient practices. In this project, good governance is defined within Deliverables “D4.1 Communication Protocols for engagement during the change process” and operationalised through:

- **Collaborative Decision-Making:** Engaging stakeholders in decision-making processes related to climate resilience initiatives, ensuring diverse perspectives are respected, considered with equity, and integrated. This participatory approach increases community ownership and legitimacy of the interventions, enhancing their long-term sustainability.
- **Capacity Building for Adaptive Governance:** Developing the capacity of local institutions and organisations to adapt to changing circumstances and effectively respond to climate-related challenges. This includes training stakeholders in adaptive governance principles, building networks of expertise, and establishing institutional frameworks that are responsive to emerging climate risks.
- **Partnership Building:** Fostering partnerships and collaborations between various stakeholders, including governments, civil society, the private sector, and individuals, to facilitate coordinated actions and resources mobilisation. Effective partnerships enhance resource availability, strengthen knowledge-sharing mechanisms, and promote resilience through collective action.

Synergy between behavioural change and good governance is essential for promoting climate resilience. While behavioural change focuses on modifying attitudes, beliefs, and practices to adapt to climate-related challenges, good governance provides the structural and institutional support needed to sustain these changes. By embedding behavioural change initiatives within governance mechanisms, the project ensures that interventions are not only effective but also enduring.

Effective governance frameworks provide accountability, transparency, and inclusivity, all of which are fundamental to fostering behavioural change. Additionally, they facilitate the alignment of policies, resources, and institutional capacities with the behavioural change goals of the project.

The iterative process of integrating governance and behavioural change will focus on gradual, sustainable progress rather than one-time activities. By starting with "quick wins," such as raising awareness and establishing baseline governance structures, followed by the incremental implementation of behavioural change initiatives, the project aims to create a strong foundation for long-term resilience as stakeholders begin to see the benefits through quick wins and so will sustain engagement.

The approach adopted in the PRO-CLIMATE project seeks to address the challenges of climate resilience through a collaborative and adaptive framework, focused on integrating behavioural change and governance improvement across different socio-ecological contexts. The project follows an innovative methodology that involves close cooperation across multiple work packages (e.g. WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5), iterative co-creation, and a strong emphasis on both local and regional scales, ensuring that the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) developed and evaluated, are not only relevant but also measurable and effective for the diverse communities involved. The next section describes the approach used to design and implement the KPIs, and the strategies in place for evaluating their effectiveness in driving positive change.

3 Conceptual Approach in PRO-CLIMATE

3.1 Collaborative Framework for Climate Resilience Assessment

The PRO-CLIMATE approach hinges on the recognition that effective climate resilience requires an integrated and holistic understanding of governance and behavioural change. The project adopts a cross-disciplinary approach where stakeholders, researchers, and experts across fields such as social sciences, environmental sciences, governance, and behavioural change are brought together to collaboratively design and implement climate resilience strategies. This framework ensures that both the technical and social dimensions of climate change are considered in tandem, reflecting the complexity and interdependencies of climate adaptation processes.

The partnership between WP4 and the other work packages (WP2, WP3, and WP5) ensures that the KPIs developed in WP4 are rigorously integrated into the various case studies, through the established Living Labs, and applied to social and ecological modelling within WP5. The iterative development of these KPIs through co-creation with stakeholders within the LLs provides critical feedback that refines the KPIs and strengthens their relevance to the specific needs of the communities involved.

3.2 Multi-Scale Integration for Diverse Contexts

One of the core principles guiding the PRO-CLIMATE approach is multi-scale integration. This involves the alignment of local, regional, and European-level frameworks to ensure that the KPIs developed in the project are universally relevant while being adaptable to the specific socio-ecological challenges of individual LLs. The diverse contexts represented by the LLs require a nuanced understanding of the specific challenges faced by diverse communities, including the differences in governance structures, stakeholder engagement practices, understanding of climate change adaptation and the level of climate resilience already achieved.

By linking local activities to regional and European frameworks, the project allows for the contextualisation of KPIs, ensuring that they are not only practical but also scalable and adaptable. This multi-scale integration approach provides a comprehensive framework for assessing climate resilience that accounts for local vulnerabilities while also ensuring alignment with broader climate goals and policies at the European level. The combination of local insights with overarching European strategies will allow for more tailored interventions and the development of effective and scalable solutions.

3.3 Iterative Co-Creation and Stakeholder Engagement

A key feature of the PRO-CLIMATE approach is the iterative co-creation process, which ensures that the perspectives of all relevant stakeholders are continually integrated into the development of KPIs and governance structures. Co-creation is a dynamic process where stakeholders, including community members, local authorities, NGOs, as well as other relevant actors, engage in continuous dialogue using their own insights to co-design solutions that are not only scientifically sound but also socially acceptable and practically feasible and sustainable.

Through regular workshops, interviews, and participatory activities, stakeholders actively contribute to the refinement of KPIs and governance measures, ensuring that the process is transparent and inclusive as well as reflective of the issues facing the communities. This ongoing engagement fosters a sense of ownership and a sense of being valued among participants, increases the legitimacy of the governance structures, and ensures that interventions are responsive to the evolving needs and aspirations of the communities they represent. The iterative nature of co-creation ensures that the KPIs are continuously updated, reflecting the changing dynamics of both the project and the socio-ecological contexts in which the LLs operate. It also fosters trust between all stakeholders.

3.4 Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration for Holistic Strategies

To achieve the goal of enhancing climate resilience, the PRO-CLIMATE approach leverages cross-disciplinary collaboration. Bringing together experts from social sciences, environmental sciences, governance, technological and behavioural change allows the project to address climate resilience from multiple angles, ensuring that solutions are comprehensive, holistic and well-rounded.

Social sciences provide valuable insights into human behaviour, community engagement, and the effectiveness of governance mechanisms, while environmental sciences contribute necessary technical expertise for assessing ecological resilience and identifying adaptive strategies. Technological expertise provides the latest developments in scientific advancement that contribute to understanding the climate changes. Behavioural change theories guide the design of interventions that aim to permanently shift attitudes and behaviours towards climate change adaptation, while governance experts focus on creating structures that are transparent, equitable, inclusive, and accountable. By combining expertise from these diverse fields, the PRO-CLIMATE project is able to develop strategies that are scientifically rigorous, socially relevant, and capable of driving long-term, sustainable change.

This cross-disciplinary approach also fosters innovation, as it encourages new perspectives and novel solutions that would not emerge from a single disciplinary focus. The collaboration between different disciplines ensures that the KPIs developed for measuring climate resilience are grounded in evidence and relevant theory from multiple fields, leading to more effective and impactful interventions.

3.5 Monitoring and Evaluation Framework

The PRO-CLIMATE project adopts a robust monitoring and evaluation framework to track progress, assess effectiveness, and adapt strategies over time. This framework is essential to ensuring that the project meets its objectives, especially as it evolves across different stages and contexts. The monitoring and evaluation process focuses on continuously assessing the performance of KPIs, identifying challenges in governance and behavioural change, and incorporating adaptive feedback mechanisms to refine the approach and ensure long-term success.

Regular assessment points are built into the project's timeline, with audits occurring after key workshops and milestones to ensure the KPIs are being implemented and measured as intended. These audits not only provide a snapshot of progress but also identify areas where improvements can be made. Through this continuous monitoring, lessons learned from, and insights gained at each stage of the project are fed back into the process, ensuring that the approach remains dynamic, responsive, and adaptable.

WP4 collaborates closely with WP2, WP3, and WP5 to ensure that the KPIs are effectively applied to the case studies (Living Labs) and integrated into social and ecological modelling within WP5. The co-creation approach used to develop and identify KPIs together with the LLs provides practical advantages for assessing behavioural change and governance effectiveness.

4 PRO-CLIMATE'S KPI Framework

This framework is designed to help Living Lab (LL) leaders and Change Agents (CAs) effectively measure governance impact, adaptability, sustainability, behavioural change, and capacity-building efforts over time. Behavioural change is a cross-cutting theme throughout the framework, recognising that governance processes and structures must actively encourage positive changes in community behaviour and engagement to enhance climate resilience and adaptation. Thus, the framework provides a structured approach for selecting (KPIs) that align with each LL's specific context, while ensuring comparability across cases by establishing a set of mandatory KPIs.

4.1 Purpose

The framework serves two main purposes:

- **Guidance for LLs:** Provide a structured approach to select and monitor KPIs related to governance structures, processes, culture, outcomes, and behavioural change. Encouraging behavioural change is fundamental to ensuring that governance measures result in practical, community-driven adaptation efforts.
- **Comparative Analysis:** To ensure at least 5 to 6 KPIs are mandatory across all LLs, enabling cross-case comparison, while also allowing LL leaders to select additional KPIs relevant to their unique contexts and behavioural change goals.

4.2 Co-Designed-Process of the KPIs

The process of developing the KPIs framework was highly collaborative, with WP4 taking the lead in drafting initial ideas on how the four key governance themes - Governance Structures, Governance Processes, Governance Culture, and Governance Outcomes - could be measured. To ensure clarity and coherence, WP3 concentrated on the focal action situation, while WP4 focused on the Living Lab (LL) level. These initial ideas were then circulated for feedback to WP5 and WP2, fostering an inclusive approach where all participants could contribute their insights, including the Project Coordinator.

Following the feedback, WP4 developed specific KPIs for each sub-theme, which were subsequently reviewed and discussed with the meeting participants before being finalised. Once the framework was established, WP2 began working on determining the appropriate methodology for measuring the KPIs within the LLs.

The finalised KPIs framework will then be presented to the change agents, who actively participate in selecting relevant KPIs using a bottom-up approach. This participatory process ensures that the chosen KPIs are meaningful and applicable to all LLs. WP2 proceeds to implement and measure the selected KPIs, aligning the assessment schedule with the workshops delivered by WP4. A detailed process has been developed to ensure integration of the framework, demonstrating the effectiveness of a well-coordinated, collaborative effort.

4.3 Themes and KPIs

The process of developing the KPI framework has been carefully structured around four key governance themes: Governance Structures, Governance Processes, Governance Culture, and Governance Outcomes, aligning with the Social-Ecological Systems (SES) framework approach. Integration of behavioural change is highlighted throughout, particularly within governance culture, stakeholder engagement, decision-making processes, and adaptability.

1. **Governance Structure:** Focuses on the engagement and efficiency of both formal and informal governance bodies, including how they encourage behavioural change through inclusive participation and community-driven initiatives.
2. **Governance Processes:** Evaluates decision-making inclusiveness, transparency, collaboration, and adherence to established norms, emphasising processes that motivate behavioural shifts toward proactive climate adaptation.
3. **Governance Culture:** Measures community values, informal practices, inclusiveness, and shared norms that influence behavioural change and promote climate-resilient practices.
4. **Governance Outcomes:** Assesses the real-world impact of governance efforts, adaptability to climate challenges, resilience, and learning capacity, including the extent to which behavioural changes contribute to sustainable governance improvements.

4.4 Table of KPIs

The Mandatory and optional KPIs are coloured coded as follows:

Mandatory KPI
Optional KPI

Table 1: Themes, sub-themes and KPIs

Theme	Sub-theme	KPI Description	Example	Measurement Method
Governance Structure	Stakeholder Engagement	No. of stakeholders actively participating in governance meetings/workshops	A coastal Living Lab focused on sustainable fisheries management hosts bi-monthly co-design workshops, engaging at least 15 key stakeholders, including local fishers, marine conservation groups, aquaculture businesses, and municipal authorities	Attendance records, meeting minutes
Governance Structure	Stakeholder Engagement	No. of community-led initiatives supported by governance structures	A rural Living Lab supports local farmers in developing sustainable soil management practices.	Number of farmer-led soil regeneration projects formally recognised by the council.
Governance Structure	Stakeholder Engagement	Level of trust between stakeholders and governance bodies	A survey includes 2-3 key trust-related questions (to be answered by community members, NGOs, and businesses):	Surveys with responses analysed for changes in trust levels.
Governance Structure	Formal Governance Bodies	Number of governance meetings held per year within the LL that include multi-stakeholder discussions on climate adaptation	In a protected wetland area municipal authorities, local farmers, environmental NGOs, tourism operators, and researchers come together at least four times per year to discuss climate-related challenges.	Review official meeting agendas, minutes, and resolutions. Additionally, identify local council decisions to implement water management policies that resulted from LL discussions.

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Theme	Sub-theme	KPI Description	Example	Measurement Method
Governance Structure	Formal Governance Bodies	Percentage of climate adaptation recommendations from the LL that are formally adopted into local or regional policies	If 10 new policies are proposed in a year and 4 include climate adaptation measures, the percentage is 40%.	Policy tracking through government reports and legislative records.
Governance Structure	Formal Governance Bodies	Number of official documents or policies influenced by the Living Lab that explicitly address climate adaptation	A regional planning document includes specific climate resilience targets for new infrastructure projects.	Policy document analysis - count the number of policies mentioning climate adaptation and assess their depth using predefined criteria.
Governance Structure	Informal Governance Bodies	Number of active community groups regularly engaging in Living Lab climate adaptation discussions, co-design activities, or decision-making	A neighbourhood sustainability group meets monthly to develop local flood resilience initiatives.	Group activity logs, participation records, meeting reports
Governance Structure	Informal Governance Bodies	Number of Living Lab governance discussions where local/traditional knowledge is presented	An indigenous elders' council is invited to share traditional water management practices in public planning meetings.	Event logs, meeting minutes, speaker records.
Governance Structure	Informal Governance Bodies	Percentage of different demographic groups (e.g., age, gender, profession) attending informal governance meetings	60% of participants in a local adaptation workshop are from underrepresented groups (youth, women, lower-income communities).	Attendance surveys, participant registration data with demographic information.
Governance Processes	Decision-Making Processes	% of decisions incorporating local stakeholder input	70% of climate adaptation policies in a city's action plan were adjusted based on feedback from resident workshops	Participation records, meeting reports, events
Governance Processes	Decision-Making Processes	Transparency score of Living Lab governance, measured by both public access to decision-making records and stakeholder	A municipality publishes 100% of climate policy meeting minutes online for public review.	Public access tracking: Measurement of the availability of decision-making records to the public through an online portal or other accessible mediums.

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Theme	Sub-theme	KPI Description	Example	Measurement Method
		perceptions of openness and accountability.		Conduct stakeholder surveys assessing perceptions of transparency, fairness, and accessibility.
Governance Processes	Collective Action and Co-operation	Number of multi-stakeholder partnerships formed within the LL for climate initiatives	A flood prevention project includes collaboration between city officials, environmental NGOs, and local businesses.	Partnership agreements, projects
Governance Processes	Collective Action and Co-operation	Percentage of climate adaptation projects originated from the LL and co-financed by multiple actors	50% of urban tree-planting projects receive funding from both public and private sources.	Number of trees planted
Governance Processes	Rules and Norms	Number of Living Lab agreements, guidelines, or informal rules established for climate adaptation	A LL of a coastal community establishes a storm resilience infrastructure agreement with municipality and local business	Reviews of types of documents or records produced and agreed
Governance Processes	Rules and Norms	Level of understanding of the community on the work undertaken by LL within the local area. Public awareness score (measured via community surveys on governance rules) – this can only be taken when something such a survey is already implemented in the LL (community).	60% of surveyed residents correctly identify key local climate adaptation policies.	Number of local residents who attend meetings organised by LL Emails and social media responses to the activities undertaken by the LL Demographics of those residents
Governance Culture	Informal Rules & Norms	Adoption rate of climate-friendly practices (measured via surveys or direct observation)	65% of surveyed households report regularly using rainwater harvesting or reducing energy consumption.	Surveys, direct observation

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Theme	Sub-theme	KPI Description	Example	Measurement Method
Governance Culture	Informal Rules & Norms	Number of climate-related discussions in informal community spaces	Local town hall meetings, religious gatherings, or neighbourhood WhatsApp groups host at least 10 climate-related discussions per year.	Meeting participation records, social media reach, interactions and engagement
Governance Culture	Values and Attitudes	% of residents considering climate action a priority	75% of respondents in a city survey agree that local government should prioritise climate adaptation in budgeting.	Survey data
Governance Culture	Values and Attitudes	Number of self-initiated climate actions per household or business	40% of businesses voluntarily implement energy-saving measures such as LED lighting and solar panels.	self-reported or observed changes
Governance Culture	Sociodemographic Inclusion	Diversity index of governance participants (age, gender, socioeconomic status)	Climate governance boards include at least 40% representation from women and marginalised communities	Keep track on these characteristics in meetings and events
Governance Culture	Sociodemographic Inclusion	Inclusion rate of vulnerable populations in climate decision-making	At least one representative from low-income communities or indigenous groups participates in all major climate policy discussions.	Keep track of the inclusion of vulnerable populations in meetings and events
Governance Outcomes	Governance Impact	Policies Implemented through tracking activities such as localised or pilot policies directly resulting from initiatives undertaken by the LLs with Climate Benefits (Tracking policy actions within one year)	Two new policies (e.g., green building incentives, water conservation rules) are implemented and actively enforced.	Policy documents, official announcements, enforcement records.

D4.2 KPIs to measure changes in capacity with respect to climate resilience

Theme	Sub-theme	KPI Description	Example	Measurement Method
Governance Outcomes	Governance Impact	Increase in Climate-Related Funding (Tracking new funding obtained of all LLs initiatives)	A 10% increase in climate-related budget allocation or at least one new funding grant secured.	Budget records, funding agreements.
Governance Outcomes	Governance Impact	Improvement in Climate Risk Awareness (Tracking knowledge improvement)	A local risk assessment is updated and shared with key stakeholders.	Existence of updated climate risk reports. If this is available.
Governance Outcomes	System Adaptability	Governance adjustments to climate challenges (Tracking new governance decisions in response to issues)	At least one governance rule (e.g., water use restrictions) is revised in response to extreme weather events.	Document review, governance, meeting minutes
Governance Outcomes	System Adaptability	Response Time to Climate Issues (Tracking speed of governance action)	New emergency response measures are put in place when a climate event happens.	Timeline tracking of response measures; emails, protocols, documentation.
Governance Outcomes	System Adaptability	Flexibility in Governance Strategies (Tracking governance adaptability)	A governance strategy (e.g., urban greening, waste management) is adjusted based on new scientific recommendations.	Documentation of reports, email exchange and meeting
Governance Outcomes	Sustainability/Anti-Fragility	Climate resilience projects sustained for LL driven initiatives (Tracking project continuation beyond initial funding)	Some ideas (e.g., flood prevention, tree planting) continue beyond its initial funding period.	Project continuation reports, emails, memorandums of commitment, cross-learning groups of change agents, follow-up assessments.
Governance Outcomes	Sustainability/Anti-Fragility	Policy Stability During Governance Changes at the LL level (Tracking whether policies remain in place when leadership changes)	No major climate-related policy is removed within the year due to political transitions.	Change of Parties due to election mean a difference regarding the support of climate change adaptation policy (interviews)
Governance Outcomes	Sustainability/Anti-Fragility	Local Climate Adaptation Leaders Identified (Tracking	Number of community members that actively promote climate	Meetings, consortiums, memorandums, certificates, participation logs.

D4.2 KPIs to measure changes in capacity with respect to climate resilience

Theme	Sub-theme	KPI Description	Example	Measurement Method
		active engagement in climate leadership roles)	adaptation practices in their sectors (e.g., schools, businesses).	
Governance Outcomes	Governance Capacity	Training and capacity building (Tracking learning and skill development)	Number of training workshops on climate adaptation are attended by governance members.	Training attendance lists, certificates of completion, Workshops delivered through WP4 and others.
Governance Outcomes	Governance Capacity	Retention of Trained Governance Members (Tracking stability in governance teams)	At least 80% of trained governance members remain in their roles after one year.	HR/governance personnel records. Are the same people on board or do they change often.; Compare the list of participants and events, change agents and key stakeholders

5 The Six Living Labs (LLs)

The six (6) LLs - Sligo, Leipzig, Badajoz, Bergen, Gdańsk, and Zakynthos - each present unique contexts and challenges for climate adaptation and resilience. To address these effectively, WP4 has implemented a comprehensive engagement strategy involving intensive collaboration with Change Agents appointed in each Living Lab. Over a period of six (6) weeks, we conducted regular bilateral meetings to discuss the specific contexts, challenges, and ideas within each Living Lab.

These discussions aimed to gather detailed information on existing strategies, identify areas of highest interest, determine what could work efficiently, and understand the visions and goals the Change Agents aim to achieve. All the insights collected during this process have been integral to the design of the KPI framework. WP4 applied the Extreme Citizen Science approach by working closely with the cases, ensuring that the process remained participatory and tailored to the needs of each Living Lab.

During these meetings, WP4 also emphasised the need for a balanced approach: while some KPIs must remain consistent across all LLs to enable cross-comparison, others should be specifically adapted to the unique contexts and objectives of each location. This collaborative approach has laid a strong foundation for developing KPIs that are both context-specific and comparable.

In the upcoming meetings, WP4 will work with the Change Agents to finalise and agree upon the KPIs, ensuring they are both relevant and actionable for driving climate resilience across all Living Labs. This process demonstrates our commitment to co-designing effective solutions through ongoing dialogue, responsiveness, and adaptation to local needs.

6 Co-Designing Sustainable KPIs: Empowering for Good Governance

6.1 Target

WP4 aims to co-design feasible and sustainable solutions with stakeholders, focusing on the most pressing social dilemmas they face in governing their social-ecological systems (SESs). This process transcends the traditional SES mapping approach, which primarily describes and analyses subsystem interactions. Instead, WP4 actively involves local stakeholders in co-designing and co-developing practical solutions through a participatory framework that integrates KPIs designed to measure good governance and behavioural change.

The approach is structured to foster participatory governance mechanisms that encourage caring behaviours and mobilise community actions, ultimately leading to measurable behavioural changes. These changes may include enhanced awareness of climate risks, increased participation in environmental initiatives, and shifts in practices such as energy conservation and sustainable land use. Measurable indicators of success might include reduced vulnerability to climate-related impacts like flooding or heatwaves, which can be tracked through surveys, community engagement rates, and climate resilience indicators.

By identifying social tipping points, WP4 aims to increase knowledge, raise awareness, and strengthen the connection between stakeholders and their environment, particularly concerning climate change and resilience. Key moments where small changes in social behaviours or norms trigger broader shifts will be identified and leveraged to accelerate change.

6.2 Methodology

The methodology, introduced to the LL in the Kick-off Workshop in November 2024, involves a structured engagement process with change agents and their guiding teams (Step 2 of the behavioural change process). By working closely together to create a shared vision of desired outcomes (Step 3), we ensure that KPIs are effectively selected and implemented.

Figure 1: Framework of Behavioural Change

This collaborative process builds upon existing governance structures while integrating KPIs that specifically measure behavioural change and good governance.

1. **Surveys:** Regularly assessing attitudes, awareness, participation, and policy support to track behavioural changes.
2. **Focus Groups and Interviews:** Engaging change agents and stakeholders to gather qualitative insights into governance processes and collective actions.
3. **Transcripts of Bilateral Meetings:** Documenting discussions and decisions made through ongoing engagement with change agents according to the communication strategy.

To facilitate this process, WP4 provides practical tools, including templates designed to help change agents keep track of activities, monitor progress, and maintain motivation.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Template for LL Gdansk to record activities undertaken November '24 to January '25							
2	Activity No	Actions Undertaken	Context	Date/Timeframe	Target	Outcome	Stakeholders Engaged	Support Required by WP4
3	1	Private chat	Discussion about Gdansk FAS and pot	04.12.2024	Collecting different opin	Being in touch' with ke	Polish Water - manager	Not yet:d
4	2	Private chat	Discussion about Gdansk FAS and pot	09.12.2024	Collecting different opin	Being in touch' with ke	Gdansk Water - manage	
5	3	Private chat	Discussion about Gdansk FAS and pot	11.12.2024	Collecting different opin	Being in touch' with ke	ARMAAG - director of t	
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Figure 2: Template for LLs to record log of activities, events and communications achieved over a 2-monthly period

D4.2 KPIs to measure changes in capacity with respect to climate resilience

These tools support Change Agents throughout the behavioural change process by providing structured approaches for collecting evidence, analysing data, and implementing KPIs effectively. In addition, WP4 has produced a suite of correspondence such as Memorandum of Understanding, Certificates and “Thank you” letters, that the LLs can use to facilitate sustained engagement of stakeholders across all LLs.

Figure 3: PRO-CLIMATE suite of correspondence

6.3 Measuring Short-term and Long-term Impact Through KPIs

To ensure comprehensive and accurate monitoring and evaluation of climate change adaptation and transformation change, WP4's KPI framework is designed to capture both short-term and long-term impacts. This approach is crucial for assessing the success of PRO-CLIMATE's initiatives, as short-term indicators provide immediate feedback, while long-term indicators demonstrate sustained progress.

Short-term KPIs are particularly useful for tracking immediate improvements in governance structures, community engagement, and awareness-raising efforts. These may include:

- **Participation Rates:** Number of stakeholders involved in decision-making processes.
- **Awareness and Knowledge Level:** Changes in understanding climate risks and governance structures.
- **Policy Adoption:** Implementation of new guidelines or frameworks developed through participatory processes.

Long-term KPIs, on the other hand, focus on the sustainability of governance mechanisms and the overall resilience of communities to climate impacts. These may include:

- **Climate Resilience Indicators:** Reduced vulnerability to floods, heatwaves, and other climate-related impacts.
- **Behavioural Change Indicators:** Persistent changes in practices such as energy conservation and sustainable land use.
- **Institutional Stability:** The durability of governance structures and their adaptability to new challenges.

The following table illustrates how different KPIs align with short-term and long-term impact measurement across the four themes:

Table 2: How different KPIs align with short-term and long-term impact

Theme	Short-term KPIs	Long-term KPIs
Governance	Participation rates, policy adoption	Institutional stability, adaptive governance
Behavioural Change	Awareness levels, community engagement	Persistent behavioural change, sustainable practices
Sustainability	Policy development, collaborative actions	Reduced vulnerability, ecological resilience
Capacity-Building	Training attendance, knowledge exchange	Institutional learning, community empowerment

By structuring the KPI framework to capture both short-term and long-term impacts, WP4 ensures a comprehensive approach to monitoring progress and adapting strategies as necessary. This dual focus aligns well with PRO-CLIMATE’s overarching mission to foster transformative change through sustained governance improvements and behavioural shifts.

6.4 Embedding KPI Selection into the Three-Fold Engagement Strategy

WP4’s communication protocols with the Change Agents are structured around a three-fold engagement strategy aimed at fostering climate resilience. Firstly, formal monthly meetings are held to discuss governance, stakeholder groups, KPI selection, and other relevant themes. Change agents can invite additional experts to enrich discussions with diverse insights and knowledge. These meetings focus on themes pertinent to ongoing climate resilience initiatives, ensuring targeted and productive interactions. Secondly, regular email exchanges provide ongoing communication to address immediate needs and support as required. The frequency of these exchanges is adjusted to suit the needs of the change agents, ensuring timely and effective support. Thirdly, a series of workshops are organised to facilitate knowledge exchange and collaboration. These workshops provide a network for change agents to share experiences, collaborate on challenges, and collect best practices. Cross-learning groups established by WP4 further support knowledge transfer and collaboration among change agents.

By embedding KPI selection and implementation into the engagement strategy, WP4 ensures that Change Agents have the tools and guidance needed to achieve their vision of improved governance and measurable behavioural change. The approach builds upon existing foundations while enhancing them with newly designed KPIs that provide valuable insights into governance effectiveness and progress toward sustainability.

7 Measurement Methods for KPIs

To ensure that the KPIs developed under WP4 are effectively measured, appropriate methodologies must be established for each KPI to accurately capture both short-term and long-term impacts. These methods are aligned with the broader goals of PRO-CLIMATE, focusing on governance structures, processes, cultures, and outcomes. The following sections outline the approach and reflect the organic nature of progress of the LLs within the PRO-CLIMATE project. As the LLs progress and gather more data and specific information, the details of implementation will become evident and available as well as how the feedback has influenced further improvements.

7.1 Baseline and Follow-Up Data Collection

Data will be collected at two key points:

- **1st Data Collection:** During the next WP4 workshop in September 2025, to establish baseline measurements of governance structures, processes, and cultures at the Living Lab (LL) level.

- **2nd Data Collection:** During the final workshop to be conducted in Month 32-33, to assess changes and evaluate progress over time.

This two-step approach allows us to compare initial and follow-up data, thereby measuring changes in governance effectiveness, behavioural changes, and adaptation progress.

7.2 Measuring Governance Structures

- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Attendance records, sign-in sheets, and meeting minutes will be analysed to measure active participation. In the long run, it can be useful to design and distribute trust surveys with targeted questions measuring confidence and transparency in governance bodies.
- **Formal Governance Bodies:** Meeting agendas, minutes, and legislative documents will be reviewed to quantify climate-related topics discussed and approved policies.
- **Informal Governance Bodies:** Analysis of activity logs, participation records, and demographic data to track inclusiveness and representation of vulnerable groups.

7.3 Measuring Governance Processes

- **Decision-Making Processes:** Comparison of decisions made with stakeholder input recorded from participation records and meeting reports.
- **Collective Action and Cooperation:** Documentation of partnerships formed, co-financed projects, and records of collaborations.
- **Rules and Norms:** Analysis of governance documents to identify revisions related to climate adaptation principles.

7.4 Measuring Governance Culture

- **Informal Rules and Norms:** Surveys or/and observation of community practices to determine the adoption of climate-friendly behaviours.
- **Values and Attitudes:** Within communities, or institutions surveys can be developed to gauge climate adaptation priorities among residents.
- **Sociodemographic Characteristics:** Analysis of governance participants' diversity and inclusiveness.

7.5 Measuring Governance Outcomes

- **Governance Impact:** Monitoring policy implementation, funding increases, and risk awareness improvements.
- **System Adaptability:** Tracking governance adjustments, response times, and strategy flexibility.
- **Sustainability and Anti-Fragility:** Long-term project continuation, policy stability, and identification of local climate leaders.
- **Governance Capacity:** Training participation, retention rates of governance members, and skill improvement over time.

This comprehensive measurement approach ensures that KPIs effectively capture the progress made towards good governance and sustainable climate adaptation.

8 Summary

The PRO-CLIMATE initiative's emphasis on co-designing sustainable KPIs with change agents offers a robust framework for monitoring progress and fostering long-term transformation. By aligning short-term and long-term KPIs with participatory governance mechanisms, the framework not only measures immediate successes but also supports the deeper, more enduring changes needed for true climate resilience. The collaborative process ensures that all stakeholders remain engaged, motivated, and equipped to drive forward positive behavioural changes. Ultimately, this integrated

approach will empower communities to build climate-resilient futures and contribute to the broader goal of sustainable development.

References

- Angelakoglou, K., Nikolopoulos, N., Giourka, P., Svensson, I. L., Tsarchopoulos, P., Tryferidis, A., & Tzovaras, D. (2019). A methodological framework for the selection of key performance indicators to assess smart city solutions. *Smart Cities*, 2(2), 269-306.
- Aguilera, R. V., & Cuervo-Cazurra, A. (2004). Codes of good governance worldwide: what is the trigger?. *Organization studies*, 25(3), 415-443.
- Aguilera, R. V., & Cuervo-Cazurra, A. (2009). Codes of good governance. *Corporate governance: an international review*, 17(3), 376-387.
- Engle, N. L., de Bremond, A., Malone, E. L., & Moss, R. H. (2014). Towards a resilience indicator framework for making climate-change adaptation decisions. *Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies for Global Change*, 19, 1295-1312.
- Ishak, Z., Fong, S. L., & Shin, S. C. (2019, October). SMART KPI management system framework. In *2019 IEEE 9th International Conference on System Engineering and Technology (ICSET)* (pp. 172-177). IEEE.
- Mosca, F., Canepa, M., & Perini, K. (2023). Strategies for adaptation to and mitigation of climate change: key performance indicators to assess nature-based solutions performances. *Urban climate*, 49, 101580.
- Nienaber, A.-M. (2020). Implementation of organisational change: Design of an 8-step organizational change process for local authorities Making Civic Initiatives Last'.
- Nienaber, A., Spundflasch, S., & Soares, A. (2020). Sustainable Urban Mobility in Europe: Implementation needs behavioural change. SUITS Policy brief 3. SUITS funded from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 690650. Mobility and Transport Research Centre, Coventry University. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341072780_SUITS_Policy_Brief_3_Sustainable_Urban_Mobility_in_Europe_-_Implementation_Needs_Behavioural_Change_Statement_of_issue
- Nienaber, A. M., Spundflasch, S., & Soares, A. E. (2023). Behavioural change in local authorities to increase organisational capacity. In: *Capacity Building in Local Authorities for Sustainable Transport Planning* (pp. 81-98). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-19-6962-1_6
- Parmenter, D. (2015). *Key performance indicators: developing, implementing, and using winning KPIs*. John Wiley & Sons.